

Focus groups 1: methodology

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Recruiting participants

We ran a series of focus groups with publishers in Q1 of 2023.

We began by compiling a list of potential participants from our networks and by asking contacts for suggestions. The aim was to have a list of around 40 people to approach, and for the list to be representative of a wide number of countries and of types of publishers.

We invited these publishers to participate, and organised the focus groups around those who had opted in.

Email 1: invitation to participate in a focus group

Checklist

- Email address
- Email subject: Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) project focus group invitation [org name]
- Bcc email address for OAPEN customer relationship management tool

Dear [NAME],

I write today on behalf of the [Book Analytics Dashboard Project](#), funded by the Mellon Foundation and led by Lucy Montgomery, Cameron Neylon, Niels Stern, Ronald Snijder, and Katherine Skinner.

This project is developing a Book Analytics Dashboard service, which is being designed in close collaboration with its stakeholder community, including its prospective future clients and customers. Publishers are among the key stakeholders of our project.

We invite you, as a key stakeholder representative, to join OAPEN and the project team for a focus group session where we'll involve you in our real-time work. During the 90 minute session, you will be able to view and use the templated demo dashboard, and provide suggestions and feedback directly to the project team. You will also hear about and provide your perspective on our plans for the service's community governance model. Your input will help us to shape the service around your needs and the needs of other publishers like you.

Please respond to this message to let us know if you can participate by next Tuesday, 31 January. If you are unable to attend but wish to suggest someone to attend in your stead, please just let us know in your reply. Once we have your reply, we will start exploring possible dates for the focus group session.

We look forward to hearing from you soon!

[name, position]

Email 1b: chasing up

I just wanted to follow up on my message to you of last week as we would love to involve you in the focus groups if you can be available. Please let me know if you would like to participate.

Email 2: scheduling

Checklist

- Email addresses in cc
- Email subject: Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) project focus group - scheduling
- Bcc LACRM [OAPEN CRM system]

Thank you for agreeing to participate in the [Book Analytics Dashboard Project](#) focus group.

This email kicks off the scheduling process, which is always the hardest part! Please complete the following:

<https://doodle.com/meeting/participate/id/bmqN610b>

We look forward to talking with you soon!

Email 2b: scheduling mop-up

This message was sent to those who didn't reply in time to the Doodle poll.

Checklist

- Email subject: Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) project focus group - time slots
- Bcc LACRM [OAPEN CRM system]

Dear colleagues,

We hope you'll join us for one of the Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) project focus groups.

We have the following time slots available:

Day	Time EST	Time GMT	TIME CET
Wed 8 Feb	08:30-10:00	13:30-15:00	14:30-16:00
Thu 9 Feb	08:30-10:00	13:30-15:00	14:30-16:00
Mon 13 Feb	08:30-10:00	13:30-15:00	14:30-16:00
Wed 15 Feb	09:00-10:30	14:00-15:30	15:00-16:30
Thu 16 Feb	09:00-10:30	14:00-15:30	15:00-16:30

Please reply to me to let me know which session you would like to join in with.

Looking forward to meeting with you soon!

Email 3: prework

Checklist

- Send this out to each group at least 2 working days before their session
- Email subject: Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) project focus group - [date]
- Bcc LACRM [OAPEN CRM system]

Dear (NAME),

We look forward to seeing you (DATE TIME) for the [Book Analytics Dashboard Project](#) focus group. [add Zoom details]

In preparation for this focus group, we ask that you please spend 15 minutes familiarizing yourself with the dashboard template and informally answering a brief set of questions.

The BAD Template Dashboard can be found here: template.book-analytics.org. It currently features University of Michigan data (thank you U of M!).

Please explore the dashboard and get familiar with the general layout of the "Overview" page, the four "drill-down" pages, and the FAQ/About page. Try and answer these three questions:

1. From the 'Overview' page, which month has the highest usage numbers when all book titles are selected?
2. From the 'Overview' page, select a book title from the filter and report the Total Access number.

3. From the 'Global Reach' page, select a country from the country filter and report on the number of Book Downloads and the number of Chapter Downloads.

Thank you so much. We look forward to seeing you soon!

Scheduling

We offered participants all the possible dates and times (90-minute slots) and asked them for their availability. When setting the groups, we aimed to separate people from the same organisation when possible. Some participants for whom English is not their mother tongue preferred to be in the same group. One participant was in a time zone with little overlap with any of the other respondents, so this session was done as more of an interview.

Logistics

The focus groups were done via Zoom, with Zoom links being sent out to participants in calendar invitations and as part of the prework email. The Zoom sessions were set to record. Laura took the facilitator role, and Katherine took notes with Sinziana helping. We used a template for recording feedback - a simple structure with space to record attendees' names, organisations, and roles, and the focus group questions noted with space to annotate.

Checklist

- Remember to update the date on the first slide of the deck before each session.

After each session

Katherine shared the recording link with Laura and Sinziana only.

After all the focus groups

Katherine transcribed the notes from each session into a synthesis document to allow contributions to be grouped by theme. Laura wrote up the summary of findings from the focus groups based on the synthesis.